

Unlocking The Full Potential of Digital Transformation: Exploring The Role of Enterprise Architecture 2.0

Jacobus van Deventer¹, Hanlie Smuts¹

¹ University of Pretoria, Pretoria, South Africa
u19056932@tuks.co.za;hanlie.smuts@up.ac.za

Abstract. The integration of digital transformation is now an essential component of achieving success for contemporary organizations. This transformative process can be leveraged to improve customer experience, streamline internal processes, boost efficiency and productivity, innovate new services and products, and formulate more effective growth strategies. However, organizations struggle with driving the adoption of new tools and processes, addressing change resistance, technology choices, security concerns and inefficient data management. Therefore, the purpose of this paper was to investigate the organizational benefits of applying Enterprise Architecture (EA) 2.0 for digital transformation. It was established that EA 2.0 promotes nine organizational benefits including strategic alignment, efficiency and optimization, decision-making and risk management, customer-centric focus, innovation and competitive advantage, change management and long-term sustainability, collaboration and communication, data management and insights, and vendor and resource management. By understanding these benefits, organizations may optimally exploit the potential value creation of using EA 2.0 for digital transformation

Keywords: Digital transformation, enterprise architecture, organizational benefits, enterprise architecture management, Society 5.0

1 Introduction

Organizations undergo an increasing level of digital transformation as technology advances [1, 2]. From automating business processes to utilizing big data analytics [3], digitalization is essential to competitiveness in today's fast-paced business world [3]. Digital transformation is defined as "a process that aims to improve an entity by triggering significant changes to its properties through combinations of information, computing, communication, and connectivity technologies" [4]. Enterprise Architecture (EA) helps organizations solve real problems faced during the digital transformation process by guiding the search for, and implementing, real solutions [5]. To understand and optimize how organizations operate, they must possess in-depth knowledge of their

Smuts, Hanlie & Hinkelmann, Knut (2024). Proceedings of the 4th Conference Society 5.0 - Innovation for Sustainable and Inclusive Social Good, Volume 2, Mauritius, 26-28 June 2024, DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.11612759

internal environment [6]. Through implementing EA, organizations can obtain the necessary knowledge of their internal business processes, procedures, technology and Information Technology (IT) architecture levels [7].

Organizations operate within environments classified into two classes: the target and external environments [6]. The external environment encompasses factors that impact organizations, but these factors are beyond the organization's ability to influence [8]. The target environmental factors can influence or initiate change in an organization and can be managed by an organization [8]. The ultimate goal of EA is to continuously align the organization's target (internal) environment with the ever-changing external-environment [9, 10]. Therefore, this study aims to consider: "*What are the organizational benefits of applying Enterprise Architecture 2.0 for digital transformation?*". By identifying the organizational benefits, organizations can understand the potential value creation of applying EA for digital transformation, while ensuring that the focus on a human-centered society stays intact [10].

The rest of the paper is structured as follows: firstly, we provide background on digital transformation and EA in section 2, followed by the methodology to identify the organizational benefits in section 3. In section 4 we provide an overview of the data analysis and findings. The paper closes with the discussion in section 5 and a conclusion in section 6.

2 Background

In the digital transformation era, controlling the architectural landscape for an organization is important. The architectural landscape guides organizations to pinpoint the problems and equips organizations with practical, digitally transformative solutions [11]. This control enables organizations to optimize their resources, ensuring they are allocated at the correct cost and time to drive digital transformation initiatives [7].

Most definitions of EA address its constituent parts, namely "enterprise" and "architecture". The Open Group bases their definition of EA on the ANSI/IEEE Std 1471-2000: "*the fundamental organization of a system, embodied in its components, their relationships to each other and the environment, and the principles governing its design and evolution*" (<https://publications.opengroup.org/>).

2.1 Society 5.0 and Enterprise Architecture 2.0

Society 5.0 aims to solve societal and economical dilemmas through combining human-centric and cyber-physical opportunities [12]. The aim of Society 5.0 therefore presupposes that transformative processes in the cyber-physical domain, will impact humans, by promoting a ubiquitous computing society and significant changes in the world of work, as well as life in general [12]. Where EA initially focused on IT implementation (EA 1.0), EA 2.0 is about a mindset and culture that focuses on the entire organization [13]. Therefore, EA 2.0 drives transformation for the whole organization, continuously mapping business key performance indicators to organizational architecture in order to enable continuous measurement and continuous improvement [2, 13].

EA frameworks offer numerous advantages by fostering a shared understanding of an enterprise system by; facilitating improved communication among stakeholders, identifying and addressing existing problems within an organizations, restructuring established organizations, redefining operations and processes, managing complex changes, integrating intricate systems, maintaining comprehensive records for future reference and collaboration, monitoring and predicting organizational performance, and overseeing operational control [14]. In essence, they serve as a comprehensive framework for optimizing enterprise functionality and ensuring effective management [2] and consist of a set of generally accepted standards that help to simplify the architecture development process and ensure that all the dimensions and perspectives are considered and are well understood by all stakeholders [14]. Examples of EA frameworks includes; the Zachman Framework for EA, the US Government's Federal Enterprise Architecture Framework (FEAF), The Open Group Architecture Framework (TOGAF), the US Department of Defence Architecture Framework (DoDAF), and the UK Ministry of Defence Architecture Framework (MoDAF) [14, 15].

An EA approach is at the forefront of facilitating, enhancing, and ensuring strategic responsiveness and agility in digital transformation [16]. This approach employs a robust and adaptable composite methodology [17] that spans the entire digital transformation journey – from defining the overarching business strategy to the successful implementation of IT assets [7].

2.2 Digital transformation and Enterprise Architecture

Digital transformation, as enabled by EA, goes beyond the technological realm [2]. It also entails a cultural shift within an organization. Embracing change becomes second nature through effective change management initiatives [18], fostering an environment where employees accept and actively contribute to the digital transformation journey [13]. One of the most compelling aspects of EA is its role in aligning an organization's IT capabilities with its digital transformation strategy [2]. This alignment empowers organizations to gain a competitive edge and sustain that advantage over rivals in the dynamic market driven by digital disruptions [19]. As organizations progress in their digital transformation journey, their EA maturity levels evolve, requiring a shift from traditional functional- and business unit-level architectures towards more comprehensive enterprise-level architecture [19]. This shift in maturity brings increased complexity and intensity, mirroring the multifaceted nature of digital transformation itself [19].

As organizations delve deeper into digital transformation, they may encounter numerous hurdles, including integrating outdated legacy systems that pose barriers to digital transformation [1]. Furthermore, effective governance and security of data sources become paramount as organizations navigate the digital terrain [20]. Additionally, cultural barriers may surface when employees resist changes brought about by new technologies and workflow transformation [21]. Effective EA strategies are important to unlocking substantial benefits in the digital transformation landscape [22]. These benefits extend to streamlined business processes, crucial for staying competitive in the digital age [23]. By ensuring the adoption of a formal EA approach and addressing the

challenges posed by digital transformation head-on, organizations can fully realize the immense potential for positive change and growth [1].

3 Research Approach

The objective of this paper to identify the organizational benefits of applying EA 2.0 for digital transformation initiatives in an organization. In order to achieve the objective, a systematic literature review (SLR) was undertaken to systematically collect, assess, and amalgamate the extensive body of research, scholarly contributions, and practical work documented by researchers, scholars, and practitioners [24]. A SLR must be conducted based on a rigorous and systematic methodological approach [25, 26]. We followed the methodological approach suggested by Boland, Cherry and Dickson [27] consisting of 3 main stages: *planning the review* (research objective definition and review protocol), *conducting the review* (primary study selections and data extraction) and *reporting the review* (report distribution) [25, 28]. The search terms applied were "enterprise architecture" and "digital transformation" and "organizational benefits" using Google Scholar and accommodating the USA and UK English "z" vs. "s" [29]. A result set of 115 papers were identified based on inclusion criteria such as peer-reviewed publications, journal papers, conference proceedings and technical reports. The corpus identified were screened by applying specific criteria such as studies not associated with the research question, anecdotal or opinion-based papers, duplicate papers and non-English studies. After the initial screening, as well as the application of inclusion and exclusion criteria, we concluded a detailed screening of abstracts and analysis of the full-text of the potential papers. A total of 48 papers were selected for an in-depth analysis and were coded and themed. This data analysis approach made it possible to thoroughly summarize and contextualize the results of various investigations, allowing the discovery of recurring themes, patterns, and qualitative insights [30].

4 Data Analysis and Findings

Data was extracted from the final corpus and expressions describing EA and digital transformation in an organizational context were extracted into an MS EXCEL worksheet. Once all the expressions extracted were identified, sub-themes and main themes were identified through two steps: firstly, descriptive codes were used to identify sub-themes [31] and secondly axial coding was used to identify emerging main themes [32]. Axial coding is the process of identifying and consolidating relationships between themes and categories that have been identified during the descriptive coding step [33]. Table 1 shows the emerging main themes, the sub-themes based on the phrases of text extracted, and the references.

Strategic alignment in EA can be likened to a lighthouse, serving as a guiding force for organizations to ensure that their digital transformation initiatives are effectively integrated with and aligned with their broader strategic goals. The importance lies in allocating resources towards technological advancements and strategically aligning these expenditures. Such resource allocation assures the appropriate concentration and

priority of efforts by facilitating the efficient allocation of resources. Moreover, within the contemporary context of the swiftly progressing digital landscape, agility is not merely a desirable quality, but an indispensable requirement. EA promotes agility by effectively integrating technology with organizational objectives and maintaining adaptability.

Table 1. Organizational benefits of applying EA 2.0 for digital transformation in Society 5.0

Main-theme	Sub-Theme	References
Strategic alignment	Strategic goal alignment: EA ensures digital transformation efforts align with the organization's strategic objectives.	[34-36]
	Resource optimization: EA helps allocate resources effectively to support digital transformation initiatives.	[5, 7, 37]
	Agility enhancement: EA fosters agility by aligning technology with business goals and promoting adaptability.	[10, 19, 38]
Efficiency and optimization	Operational efficiency: EA identifies process optimization and automation areas, reducing operational costs.	[7, 18, 39]
	Complexity reduction: EA promotes standardization and simplification, reducing organizational complexity.	[36, 40]
	Cost savings: Through optimization, EA can reduce costs across the organization.	[41, 42]
Decision-making and risk management	Informed decision-making: EA provides a structured framework for informed technology decisions.	[43, 44]
	Risk mitigation: EA identifies and addresses risks associated with digital transformation projects.	[45-47]
	Compliance and Governance: EA helps enforce compliance and governance policies.	[48, 49]
Customer-centric focus	Enhanced customer experience: EA guides the development of customer-centric digital solutions.	[1, 50]
	Data-driven insights: EA supports data integration and management for personalized customer interactions.	[23, 51]
Innovation and competitive advantage	Innovation enablement: EA identifies opportunities for innovation through emerging technologies.	[9, 11, 52]
	Competitive edge: EA enables rapid response to market changes and delivers innovative solutions.	[8, 16, 53]
Change management and long-term sustainability	Change management support: EA provides a roadmap for transitioning to new technologies and processes.	[17, 54, 55]
	Long-term sustainability: EA ensures digital transformation initiatives are adaptable to evolving needs.	[56, 57]
Collaboration and communication	Enhanced collaboration: EA fosters collaboration among business units and departments.	[58, 59]
	Communication framework: EA serves as a common language for effective communication.	[8, 22]

Data management and insights	Data analytics: EA supports data integration and analysis for informed strategies.	[20, 60]
	Security and compliance: EA assist in securing and managing data in compliance with regulations.	[61, 62]
Vendor and resource management	Vendor management: EA provides vendor selection, negotiation, and alignment insights.	[3, 63]
	Resource efficiency: EA ensures the efficient allocation of resources to support digital transformation.	[4, 6, 21]

Operational inefficiencies can frequently deplete resources and hinder efforts towards change, emphasizing the importance of efficiency and optimization. The utilization of EA reveals these inefficiencies, presenting opportunities for enhancing and automating processes. The outcome frequently entails a noteworthy decrease in operational expenditures. Furthermore, EA mitigates organizational complexity by promoting uniformity and discouraging redundancy. This simplification process subsequently results in concrete cost reductions across diverse company divisions.

The significance of *decision-making and risk management* in digital transformation cannot be overstated. EA provides a comprehensive and systematic perspective, allowing stakeholders to make informed and rational choices. However, selecting appropriate choices is not solely limited to decision-making but also encompasses comprehending and effectively managing the potential hazards. EA is crucial in proactively identifying and mitigating these hazards. In a contemporary context where the importance of adherence to rules and governance policies cannot be underestimated, EA takes proactive measures to guarantee that technology decisions align with these requirements.

In the contemporary era of digitalization, the consumer has a paramount position of authority and influence. EA plays a crucial role in helping organizations shift their focus from being solely technology-centric to becoming *customer-centric*. EA prioritizes facilitating customer-centric digital efforts by implementing solutions that improve the customer experience and enable data integration for more tailored interactions. [50].

The relationship between *innovation and competitive advantage* is such that today's breakthroughs become the minimum requirements for success in the future. EA plays a pivotal role in diligently surveying the landscape for promising opportunities, particularly those arising from emerging technologies. It facilitates the ability of organizations to sustain a competitive advantage by enabling them to promptly adapt to market dynamics through innovative solutions.

The concept of *change management* is closely intertwined with the long-term sustainability of digital transformation. EA offers a strategic framework that enables organizations to effectively navigate and anticipate changes rather than reactively responding to them. This approach guarantees the achievement of long-term sustainability, as digital initiatives possess the capacity to be scaled and adjusted to meet future requirements.

Collaboration and communication are frequently hindered by silos within expansive organizational structures. EA effectively eliminates these boundaries, cultivating a cooperative atmosphere across various organization units and departments and using EA as a shared medium facilitates enhanced and cohesive communication.

Through the generation of significant sets of data, the acquisition of insights holds immense value. The *integration and analysis of data* are strongly advocated by EA, as they empower organizations to extract practical solutions from their data. Security measures must not be neglected or marginalized due to the growing prevalence of data breaches. It must be ensured that data is utilized securely and effectively managed in compliance with regulatory requirements.

Vendor and resource management are integral components of digital transformation, as it is not a solitary endeavour. External partners and vendors frequently assume a pivotal position in this process. EA provides valuable insights into the management of vendors, ensuring that external partnerships align with internal aims. Furthermore, by optimizing resource allocation, EA guarantees the utmost efficiency in utilizing human and technical resources to facilitate digital transformation.

5 Discussion

In order to assess the efficacy of strategic alignment, it is imperative to commence by evaluating the proportion of IT efforts that align with broader organizational objectives. This analysis offers a concise overview of how much technology projects align with the organization's objectives. In addition, the resource usage rate provides valuable insights into the effectiveness of resource allocation in transformation endeavours. Furthermore, agility, an essential principle of strategic alignment, may be effectively measured by evaluating the duration it takes to bring new initiatives to the market. This measure emphasizes the speed at which an organization can adapt and implement modifications.

When focusing on efficiency and optimization, observable outcomes frequently manifest as reductions in operating costs. The effectiveness of EA is evidenced by the direct correlation between its implementation and the reduction in operating expenses, as it pushes process improvements and system overhauls. The metric of system standardization rate, which represents the proportion of processes or systems that have been standardized through the implementation of EA, emerges as a crucial indicator. Furthermore, cost avoidance in EA emphasizes the proactive benefits of preventing needless or duplicative technology expenditures, as it quantifies the savings obtained from such actions.

In the context of decision-making and risk management, the proactive identification and subsequent mitigation of high-risk issues indicate the effectiveness and strength of risk management protocols. In addition to this, the metric of decision-making time has great significance. Organizations can assess the effectiveness and efficiency of their decision-making processes in the context of EA by quantifying the average duration required to reach critical decisions.

These metrics provide a comprehensive and targeted method for evaluating the impact and effectiveness of EA within the context of digital transformation. By analyzing these indicators, organizations can assess the present efficacy of EA and pinpoint areas that require additional refinement and improvement.

6 Conclusion

The aim of this paper was to identify the organizational benefits of applying EA 2.0 for digital transformation initiatives in an organization. A corpus of 48 identified papers were analyzed and organizational benefit themes were identified. The analysis identified 9 organizational benefits (themes) consisting of 21 sub-themes. The advent of the digital era has ushered in ground-breaking innovation, unparalleled expansion, and digitalization asserting organizations to consider their digital transformation strategies. By understanding and considering the organizational benefits of applying EA 2.0 in this context, EA 2.0 signifies a paradigm change in which organizations adopt technology and integrate it into their operations. This study provides further evidence of the importance of structure, strategy, and synchronization in effectively utilizing digital capabilities, with EA 2.0 playing a central role.

It must be acknowledged that the analysis in this study was constrained by a specific choice of keywords ringfencing the corpus extracted for analysis. The organizational benefits list may therefore not comprehensively include all aspects of digital transformation and the impact of EA. In addition, specific organizations, depending on their maturity, may place different importance on certain aspects. However, the limitations also direct further research opportunities. Firstly, the organizational benefits identified may be applied and tested in different organizations to establish the completeness of the identified list and secondly, a scale based on organizational maturity may be developed to further operationalize the findings from this study.

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